

INITIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH POLYARTICULAR FORM OF JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Relevance of the problem. A chronic inflammatory joint disease, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA), is a major problem in modern pediatric rheumatology. The relevance of studying JRA is determined by its relatively high prevalence among other rheumatic diseases of childhood and the high incidence of early disability, which reduces the child's and parents' quality of life, leading to negative personal and social consequences [1]. Furthermore, in recent years, there has been an increase in the primary incidence of rheumatic diseases, including JRA [4]. In other words, JRA represents an important medical and social problem. It should be noted that among the variants of the disease classified under the heading of JRA, a special place is occupied by the polyarticular form, which is often characterized by a steadily progressive course and an unfavorable prognosis [2].

Despite undeniable advances in the pharmacotherapy of JRA, this problem remains one of the most challenging areas of pediatric rheumatology, requiring further study. Currently, rheumatologists have a fairly extensive arsenal of anti-inflammatory drugs. However, none of them can radically alter the course and outcome of the disease. Therefore, the primary goal of pharmacotherapy for JRA is to find new drugs or optimal combinations of known medications that can quickly and effectively suppress the immune-inflammatory process and prevent disease progression.

In recent years, there has been renewed interest in the use of glucocorticoids (GCs) in rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The "renaissance" of systemic GC therapy is explained by the fact that GCs are currently the most potent anti-inflammatory drugs and, in addition, have immunomodulatory properties [3]. At the same time, much attention from researchers is being paid to studying the effectiveness of low doses of GCs. It has been shown that in RA, low doses of GCs have optimal anti-inflammatory activity and are relatively safe [21, 28, 56, 64, 158]. At the same time, data are accumulating on the basic (disease-modifying) effect of low doses of GCs [9, 10, 28, 116, 180]. Moreover, in some patients, low doses of GCs may have an anti-protective effect by reducing the severity of inflammation and improving joint mobility [1].

The aim of the study was to evaluate the efficacy and safety of systemic GC therapy in the complex treatment of patients with polyarticular juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

Study objectives: To evaluate the clinical efficacy of GC in the combination therapy of polyarticular juvenile rheumatoid arthritis.

Study results. Based on long-term observation (20 months on average) of 89 patients with polyarticular juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA) with a disease duration of less than 5 years, who received GC in combination with MT and NSAIDs (n=46) and were treated with MT and NSAIDs (n=43), it was established that:

Systemic GC therapy (initial dose - 0.3-0.6 mg/kg body weight per day of prednisolone, low maintenance dose - 0.1-0.2 mg/kg body weight of prednisolone) is an effective method for treating the polyarticular form of JRA.

Very good and good treatment results were noted in 58.7% and 41.3% of patients treated with GC in combination with MT and NSAIDs, respectively, compared with 18.6% and 30.2% of patients receiving MT and NSAIDs ($p < 0.001$).

The inclusion of GC in the therapeutic complex made it possible to reliably reduce the frequency of intra-articular injections of GC ($p < 0.001$), and 58.7% of children did not require local GC therapy.

Effective suppression of rheumatoid inflammation made it possible to discontinue NSAIDs in 43.5% of patients on average after 8.8 months and GC in 28.3% of children on average after 16.1 months.

A slowdown in the progression of osteochondral destruction of joints was found in 89.1% of patients receiving low doses of GC in combination with MT, compared with 62.8% of patients treated with MT alone ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusions: A short-term initial dose of GC and a long-term, alternating low maintenance dose of GC are virtually safe.

Indications for the appointment of systemic GC therapy for the polyarticular form of JRA are disease activity of stage II-II, lack of effect from previous treatment with NSAIDs and basic agents.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Starikova, A.V. Clinical and immunological criteria for predicting the course, outcomes and choice of treatment tactics for uveitis associated with joint damage in children: Abstract of a PhD thesis. – M., 2023. – 14 p.
2. Teplova S.N. The role of impaired immune response regulation processes in the pathogenesis of uveitis associated with rheumatic diseases / E.A. Drozdova, S.N.Teplova // Bulletin of ophthalmology. - 2018. - No. 3 (124). - P. 23-26.
3. Trunov, A. N. Cytokine imbalance in the lacrimal fluid in patients with autoimmune uveitis / A. N. Trunov, N. S. Arbenyeva, A. L. Shvayuk et al. // Bulletin of the Orenburg State University. - 2013. - No. 4 (153). - P. 270 - 273.
4. Edelsten, C. Epidemiology of visual loss in pediatric uveitis / C. Edelsten, M. Stanford, E. Graham // XXXIX International Congress of ophthalmology. – Sydney, 2013 – P.138.